

SEVENTH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

THEME [FP7-ENERGY-2011-1]

***Deliverable D8.4/6.3 “Common recommendations to
ENTSO-E regarding TSO & RSCI rules for business
processes and data exchange”***

Project acronyms: iTesla / UMBRELLA

Project full titles: **Innovative Tools for Electrical System Security
within Large Area**

**Toolbox for Common Forecasting, Risk
assessment, and Operational Optimization in
Grid Security Cooperation of Transmission
System Operators (TSOs)**

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List of abbreviations

CGMES	Common Grid Model Exchange Standard
CIM	Common Information Model
CIM ID	Common Information Model Identifier
D2CF	2 Day Ahead Congestion Forecast
DACF	Day-ahead Congestion Forecast
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DEF	Data Exchange Format
DTS	Dispatcher Training Simulator
DSO	Distribution system operator
EMS	Energy Management System
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
FACTS	Flexible AC Transmission System
FP7	7th Framework Programme
HVDC	High-Voltage Direct Current
IDCF	Intraday Congestion Forecast
NC OS	Network Code on Operational Security
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
PSTs	Phase shifting transformers
RG CE	ENTSO-E Regional Continental Europe
RSCI	Regional Security Coordination Initiative
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SVC	Static Var Compensator
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UCTE	Union for the Co-ordination of Transmission of Electricity

Executive Summary

Transmission system operators (TSOs) face new challenges in the day to day grid operation and operational planning. Security issues of the pan-European electricity transmission system are likely to become more and more challenging in the coming years due to:

- The growing contribution of less predictable and intermittent renewable energy sources (RES) e.g. wind and photovoltaic generation.
- The introduction and the need for coordination of additional controllable devices such as phase shifting transformers (PSTs), high-voltage direct-current (HVDC) lines, flexible AC transmission system (FACTS)...
- A partially controllable electricity demand.
- The increasing difficulty to build new overhead transmission lines.
- The progressive construction of a single European electricity market.
- Market mechanisms which do not cover system security aspects, leading to high deviations between scheduled and physical flows.

These new constraints but also new opportunities will result in more complex transmission system operation, a system working closer to its operational limits, a more frequent use of remedial actions in order to relieve congestions and therefore a need for a major revision of operational rules and procedures. Furthermore, meteorological forecasts are error-prone and the respecting feed-ins from RES lead to deviations of the load flow situations from anticipated system states. Especially in stressed system situations, forecast errors can lead to unforeseen violations of operating limits and might trigger cascading outages as a worst case. In this context, it is clear that currently available tools for security assessment will no longer be suitable for network operators to take the right decisions within this changing operational framework. Moreover, Regional Security Cooperation Initiatives (RSCIs) have already emerged for different regions of the pan-European transmission system (such as Coreso, SSC and TSC)¹. These coordination initiatives will not be fully efficient without a new generation of tools allowing the different TSOs to increase coordination.

Over the past four years the iTesla and UMBRELLA projects have developed toolboxes in order to ensure secure grid operation also in future electricity networks with high penetration of intermittent RES. Based on these collaborative projects, this deliverable proposes common recommendations to European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) regarding TSO & RSCI rules for business processes and data exchange, which addresses the need to meet necessary requirements for TSOs and DSOs to improve the interoperability and security in the pan-European grid system.

¹ Coreso: Coordination of Electricity System Operators
SSC: Security Service Centre
TSC: TSO Security Cooperation

This deliverable is a report of the common work done in the framework of the iTesla and the UMBRELLA projects. As output of this common deliverable we are focusing on:

Recommendation 1: Exchange of stationary data in common grid model exchange standard format.

European TSOs should exchange stationary data of their respective system in CGMES format as soon as possible. Identifiers of network elements should be unique and persistent across the datasets in order to be able to perform an advance security assessment.

Recommendation 2: Enhanced data format and network modelling.

When exchanging data using the CGMES format, European TSOs should use persistent identifiers for equipment in order to be able to match them with additional data automatically (e.g. dynamic and economic data). The incorporation of the additional information, like redispatch potential, should be considered in the further development of CGMES. Aggregation of injections (loads and generation units, also RES) should be avoided, whenever possible, and forbidden for large generation units.

Furthermore a common understanding and as far as possible a harmonization regarding the detail of grid modelling should be sought by the TSOs.

Recommendation 3: Exchange of remedial actions in stationary data.

In addition to stationary data of their respective system, European TSOs should exchange a list of contingencies to be simulated or the methodology to determine the contingencies as well as a catalogue of relevant remedial actions. Moreover a harmonization of the merit order of remedial actions is needed to be able to get common proposals of remedial actions from the new tools developed by iTesla and UMBRELLA. The exchange format needs to be consistent with the description of the system (use of CGMES with unique and persistent identifiers).

Recommendation 4: Exchange of dynamic data in the future transmission system operation.

European TSOs should exchange dynamic data of their respective system to be able to run time domain simulations on all or parts of the European system in the framework of systematic security assessment of system situations from D-2 to close to real time.

Recommendation 5: Recommendation regarding the format of exchange of dynamic data.

In the short term, European TSOs should exchange dynamic data using standard or “user defined” models in the format they use for their internal dynamic studies.

Recommendation 6 (iTesla): Long term solution proposed for the exchange format of dynamic data among European TSOs.

European TSOs should exchange CGMES files of their respective system and it is proposed to encourage the power system community to use the open source iTesla Power System MODELICA[®] library to be able to run time domain simulations on all or

parts of the European system using MODELICA[®] language compliant simulation engine.

Recommendation 7: Risk management and reliability criteria.

European TSOs should be encouraged to develop and include common risk-based criteria for security assessment in their operational planning process and real-time operation. In particular, these criteria should include data related to reliability and/or failure rates of equipment, estimates of the (cost of) energy not served, as well as more comprehensive forecasts to describe uncertainties from RES, load and intra-day trading.

Recommendation 8: Defence and restoration plans.

European TSOs are encouraged to continue the ongoing work towards harmonization of defence plans and restoration procedures, and consider to integrate solutions for coordinated power flow control of embedded HVDCs to dampen inter-area oscillations, over-frequency control of renewable generation and frequency control of consumption to defend the frequency stability, and use of PMU information for early detection of voltage instability and use tools for automated tuning of out-of-step relays. There is also a need to consider the impact of the steadily increasing amount of distributed generation on the existing load shedding schemes. Finally, the TSOs should consider using automatically computed coordinated restoration plans taking into account dynamics and further investigate possibilities of using AC and DC connected controllable wind power plant to speed up restoration.

Recommendation 9: Amendment of operational security processes & tools:

The experience of the TSOs shows that for the successful daily operation the European TSOs should further develop and harmonize their processes regarding operational planning and real-time operation, incorporating the preferable functionalities from the research projects.

Support from legal and regulatory side is needed in order to achieve the best possible solutions in terms of a European optimum. The most promising approach in order to achieve this is a strong cooperation among the national regulations authorities.

The Network Codes, especially the Network Code on Operational Security (NC OS), drafted by the ENTSO-E and enacted by the European Commission were an important step along the path of the harmonization of legal/regulatory frameworks within the European electricity system. But in order to achieve the best possible solutions in terms of a European optimum of flexibility and security of the transmission system operation a further harmonization and clarification is needed, which is not addressed in this level of detail by the network codes.

1 Outline and framework of both projects

The iTesla and UMBRELLA projects are different collaborative research projects, supported in large part by European Union (EU) funding in the context of the 7th Framework programme (FP7). Both projects started in January 2012 for a period of 4 years and are linked to Topic ENERGY.2011.7.2.1 of the ENERGY-2011-1 Call and are part of the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) Research and Development Plan and the European Electricity Grid Initiative (EEGI) Roadmap (www.itesla-project.eu; <http://www.e-umbrella.eu>).

The iTesla project is coordinated by RTE the French transmission system operator (TSO). The 21 European partners in the iTesla project are the following:

- 6 national transmission system operators (TSO): RTE (France), Elia (Belgium), National Grid (UK), REN (Portugal), Statnett (Norway) and IPTO (Greece),
- 1 Regional coordination service centre: Coreso (Belgium),
- 6 universities and research centres: Imperial College (UK), INESC Porto (Portugal), KTH (Sweden), KU Leuven (Belgium), RSE (Italy), DTU (Denmark),
- 8 industrial R&D providers: AIA (Spain), Artelys (France), Bull (France), Pepite (Belgium), Quinary (Italy), Gridquant (Spain), Tractebel Engineering (Belgium), Technofi (France).

The UMBRELLA project is coordinated by TenneT TSO GmbH, one of the four German TSOs. The 15 European partners in the UMBRELLA project are:

- A large-scale group of nine TSOs: TenneT TSO GmbH (Germany), Amprion (Germany), CEPS AS (Czech Republic), Elektro-Slovenija D.O.O (Slovenia), TransnetBW GmbH (Germany), Polskie Sieci Elektroenergetyczne S.A. (Poland), Swissgrid AG (Switzerland), TenneT TSO B.V. (Netherlands), APG – Austrian Power Grid AG (Austria).
- Five universities and one research centre providing sound scientific knowledge and research know-how: Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), ETH Zurich (Switzerland), Graz University of Technology (Austria), RWTH Aachen (Germany), University of Duisburg-Essen (Germany) and Forschungsgemeinschaft für Elektrische Anlagen und Stromwirtschaft e.V. (Germany).

2 Presentation and description of iTesla and UMBRELLA project toolboxes and relevant results

2.1 iTesla toolbox

2.1.1 Project presentation

The iTesla project has developed a novel toolbox able to support the operation of the pan-European grid in the coming years and is validating the different functionalities of this toolbox with datasets of increasing complexity and size. More precisely, this toolbox has been designed to support the decision-making process from two-days ahead to real time and to take up the following three main challenges:

- to perform accurate security assessment taking into account the dynamics of the system using time-domain simulations,
- to provide a risk-based assessment taking into account the different sources of uncertainties (in particular, those brought by intermittent power generation), the probabilities of contingencies and the possible failures of corrective remedial actions,
- to provide operators with relevant proposals of preventive and corrective remedial actions to keep the system in a secure state e.g. such as generation redispatching, change in transformer tap position, topology of substations, set point values of high-voltage direct-current (HVDC) lines or phase shifting transformers (PSTs).

This toolbox has been designed to be used by a single TSO, by a coordination centre such as Coreso or by a group of TSOs working in a coordinated way.

In addition to the above objectives, the iTesla project has developed:

- Methodologies and tools for validation of dynamic models of components of the pan-European system, using off-line analysis; these tools have been designed to determine model parameters using measured dynamic responses of the grid.
- New concepts to build more robust defence plans and optimal restoration plans with the help of automated tools e.g. the integration of renewable energy sources (RES)/ distributed energy resources (DER) and the use of time-synchronized measurements from phasor measurement units (PMUs).

2.1.2 Toolbox results

The outcomes of the iTesla project can be grouped into four main subsets:

1. The iTesla toolbox for network security assessment,
2. Several tools for validation of power system dynamic models,
3. A library of power system models in MODELICA[®],
4. Recommendations and software tools for improvement of defence and restoration plans.

The project website (www.itesla-project.eu) presents an interactive way to navigate through the description of these main outcomes.

Figure 1: Top-level page to navigate through the iTesla outcomes.

- The iTesla toolbox for network security assessment is able to take into account simultaneously the uncertainties affecting power injections and the dynamic behaviour of the grid. The computations are performed with two complementary platforms: the online and offline platforms:

Figure 2: iTesla online and offline platforms.

The offline platform builds security rules that are based on an extensive analysis of a large number of system states that are likely to occur. The online platform uses these “offline rules” to identify the contingencies for which corrective or preventive remedial actions are needed and for which accurate time-domain simulations must be performed online. Both platforms consist of different modules, each fulfilling a specific technical function, as well as common services such as data conversion, data management, data mining, or graphical user interfaces. All software bricks will be distributed by the project partners, either under open source licenses or as commercial products.

- **Tools for validation of power system dynamic models:**

The developed RaPId tool prototype attempts to tune the model’s parameters so as to satisfy a fitness criterion (e.g. minimize the error between simulation and measurement traces) between the outputs of the simulation and the experimental measurements of the same outputs provided by the user.

- 1 Output (and optionally input) measurements are provided to RaPId by the user.
- 2 At initialization, a set of parameter is generated randomly or preconfigured in RaPId.
- 3 The model is simulated with the parameter values given by RaPId.
- 4 The outputs of the model are recorded and compared to the user-provided measurements.
- 5 A fitness function is computed to judge how close the measured data and simulated data are to each other
- 2' Based on the fitness computed in (5) a new set of parameters is computed by RaPId

Figure 3: The RaPId tool prototype for model validation.

Tools for validation of very large power system models have also been developed. By using a version of the dynamic power system simulation tool EUROSTAG® that incorporates the algorithmic advances from the PEGASE² project, exploiting high performance computing (HPC), and using automated calculations and result analysis, it is possible to validate power systems as large as the European interconnected system.

Figure 4: Validation of very large power system models.

- In the framework of the project, a **MODELICA® Library of power system component models** has been built with all the dynamic models used by iTesla TSOs, namely Statnett (Norway), REN (Portugal), IPTO (Greece), Elia (Belgium), and RTE (France), either with PSS®E, PSAT® or EUROSTAG®. All those models have been implemented into a MODELICA® equivalent model and validated against their PSS®E, PSAT® and EUROSTAG® reference models. This MODELICA® Library of power system component models is about to be released open source so that it can be used and enriched by TSOs and the whole power systems community.

- The **iTesla recommendations regarding defence plans** are gathered into the following available document: Deliverable D6.2 *“Improvement of defence plans in European power systems - Proposed harmonization, coordination and inclusion of RES, distributed resources and PMU information”* [1].

In the framework of the iTesla project, Tractebel Engineering and AIA have coupled their respective tools FAST DTS and AGORA in a proof of concept tool. FAST DTS is a dynamic dispatcher training simulator and AGORA is a system for the automatic calculation of optimal restoration plans among other advanced energy management system (EMS) functions. This proof of concept is used to test and validate restoration plans proposed by AGORA on the real-time dynamic simulator FAST DTS and to conduct joint research on hierarchical restoration plans.

² PEGASE project: Pan European Grid Advanced Simulation and State Estimation (in the context of the FP7)

Figure 5: AGORA/FAST DTS (Dispatcher Training Simulator) tool for validation of restoration plans.

2.2 UMBRELLA Toolbox

2.2.1 Project presentation

UMBRELLA [2] is an EC FP7 project that provides a toolbox prototype for TSOs to ensure secure grid operation also in future electricity networks with high penetration of intermittent RES. It enables TSOs to act in a coordinated European target system where regional strategies converge to ensure the best possible use of the European electricity infrastructure.

Figure 6: UMBRELLA consortium partners.

TSOs face new challenges in the day to day grid operation and operational planning. Pan-European market activities and resulting cross-border flows as well as the growing utilization of decentralized energy resources lead to increasing power transits and bring the transmission grid closer to its technical limits. As a consequence, security margins become smaller and TSOs are frequently applying remedial measures in order to relieve congestions. Furthermore, meteorological forecasts are error-prone and the respecting feed-ins from RES lead to deviations of the load flow situations from anticipated system states. Especially in stressed system situations, forecast errors can lead to unforeseen violations of operating limits and might trigger cascading outages as a worst case.

The straight forward way to cope with growing uncertainties is to enlarge the security margins accordingly. Yet too large security margins should be avoided because of their economical inefficiency. However, too small security margins will endanger the system security.

Due to this, a reasonable way to deal with uncertainties is to wait as long as possible and apply remedial actions only if critical deviations from anticipated system states actually occur. However, situations with an insufficient availability of remedial actions have to be avoided.

Therefore, it is necessary to use adequate security margins and provide sufficient system flexibility within the day-ahead transmission grid operational planning. To do so, TSO must brace themselves for all possible upcoming system states and apply measures with long activation timeframes in advance. Particularly, power plant start-up decisions must be made up to several days in advance when uncertainties are significant. Additionally, robust switching states have to be chosen to maintain the flexibility of applying switching measures to ensure system security.

Figure 7: Main features of the UMBRELLA Toolbox.

UMBRELLA has developed an innovative toolbox prototype to support the decentralised grid security approach of TSOs, giving the opportunity to increase cooperation when facing the increased complexity in system's operation. A decentralised network security analysis with everyone "on board" looking at the same results and evaluating solutions in a coordinated and optimised way increases the efficiency of the network operation. Furthermore, UMBRELLA methodologies provide a step forward in the evaluation of uncertainties and their impact in different operational timeframes, the introduction of risk-based assessment and optimisation of remedial actions. This toolbox, to be used in different operational timeframes, includes:

- Modelling and simulation of uncertainties due to market activities, RES on different time scales (RES forecast) and outages

- Development of risk based assessment concepts for anticipated system states with and without corrective remedial actions under consideration of probabilistic distributions.
- Security constrained, time-coupled optimal power flow algorithms in order to find the optimal remedial actions on different time scales mitigating forecasted risks, minimizing total costs and maximizing transmission capacities

2.2.2 Toolbox results

In order to evaluate the different functionalities of the UMBRELLA toolbox a stepwise approach was chosen, where the TSOs and research partners participated.

Figure 8: First preparation step for the test cases by the TSOs and the research partners.³

The major outcomes of the tests are described in the UMBRELLA Deliverable 6.2 “*Evaluation of the UMBRELLA Toolbox*” and can be summarized as follows:

- Processes for exchange of data have been put in place and necessary improvements of data quality compared to the current practice have been identified.
- The optimization algorithm is able to find effective remedial measures. Either by proposing an optimal subset of previously defined topological measures, or by efficient redispatch proposals for violations, which could not be resolved by solely applying topological measures.
- Depending on the target-timeframe the optimization algorithm is also able to account for time-coupling constraints and probabilistic uncertainties.
- The probabilistic and risk-based security assessment offers a significant amount of additional information to the operators (Figure 10). The further implementation of these functionalities therefore should be done in a parallel run in order to get the stakeholders used to new possibilities (Figure 9).

³ SUCs: System Use Cases

Classic path (c.f. DACF process):

Modern path:

➤ Comparison results

Figure 9: Parallel run of the manual work by operators, and the approach based on the UMBRELLA toolbox incorporating the new functionalities, e.g. the (semi-) automated, security constrained optimal power flow algorithms to enable comparability.

Possible improvements, e.g. the data quantity and quality issues, the different ranking of remedial actions depending on different national legal/regulatory frameworks and other were identified during the testing phase. After the harmonization with the colleagues from iTesla, they were incorporated in this deliverable.

Figure 76: Lost active load for Study Case 1 (output detailed analysis).

Figure 77: Lost reactive load for Study Case 1 (output detailed analysis).

Figure 80: Four levels of risk and their corresponding probabilities for Study Case 1 (output detailed analysis).

Figure 81: Probability of cascading events, overloaded circuits and voltage violations for Study Case 2 (output screening tool).

Figure 10: Results from detailed risk assessment based on AC power flow and Monte Carlo sampling for a specific operating point with sensitivities [UMBRELLA Deliverable 4.3, page 120].

Also modelling of pump storage plants and HVDC is not suited for proper creation and analysis of system use cases. Currently the pumps of pump storage plants are modelled as “ordinary load”. A simple flag marking them as pumps would already be sufficient in order to do some proper calculations; also the modelling of (cross-border) HVDC-lines as load or infeed hampers the automated optimization.

So far datasets used in the DACF process were not really suited for the analysis of voltages. Therefore, a sufficient amount of voltage controlled nodes and realistic target voltages should be introduced in the datasets. Equipment for reactive power compensation (capacitor bank, shunt reactors ...) should be modelled explicitly.

Furthermore a more detailed modelling of generators and their associated transformers should be performed, instead of just using an equivalent network infeed. Fundamental electrical parameters like P_{\min} , P_{\max} , Q_{\min} , Q_{\max} or, even better, a capability curve of each generator, are needed for the electrical part of the forecast. In order to perform market simulations and calculate an optimal redispatch, additional information is needed. For power plants the primary fuel type, efficiency, costs (marginal & start-up), time constraints (start-up, max/min up time, min down time ...) are vital for doing time coupled optimization.

The unavailability of power plants should be provided in order to take it into account for the (cost based) redispatch optimisation. E.g. if a power plant is unavailable, the P_{\min} and P_{\max} should be 0 (zero) or a “revision” flag should be activated. Even better is the value of the remaining capacity of the power plant.

The redispatch information should also include the following details per unit:

- Indicative prices for increase (sell) and decrease (buy, which means negative redispatch costs) of the infeed per MWh.
- Free dispatchable power.
- Lead times for the start-up of power plants and minimum downtime.
- Information about must-run units including the minimum active power.
- Information about reserve-power booked on the units.
- Ranking indicator to mark which power plants shall be excluded or taken into account with a lower priority for redispatch optimisation due to technical constraints (also legal or regulatory ones, if applicable).

The redispatch potential (increasing and decreasing) per unit should be exchanged on a regular basis. Thus the amount of redispatch proposed by the tool is consistent with the possibilities in real-time operation. This requires transparent and reliable input files which include the planned schedule, redispatch potentials and time constraints for each power plant.

Different TSO-strategies concerning operational limits of equipment need to be considered. E.g. if there is a changing current limit due to an installed thermal line monitoring or if there are season dependent PATL or TATL values⁸, or the security margin until the automatic activation of protection devices. So far there is some commonly used wording. Nevertheless further

⁸ PATL: Permanent Admissible Transmission Loading

TATL: Temporary Admissible Transmission Loading

harmonization on the understanding and the implementation of the different operational strategies of the TSOs are needed in order to incorporate them into the tools properly. Otherwise a reasonable, automatic optimization is not possible.

Recommendation 2

When exchanging data using the CGMES format, European TSOs should use persistent identifiers for equipment in order to be able to match them with additional data automatically (e.g. dynamic and economic data). The incorporation of the additional information, like redispatch potential, should be considered in the further development of CGMES. Aggregation of injections (loads and generation units, also RES) should be avoided, whenever possible, and forbidden for large generation units.

Furthermore a common understanding and as far as possible a harmonization regarding the detail of grid modelling should be sought by the TSOs.

3.3 Exchange of remedial actions in stationary data

REMEDIAL ACTIONS are defined in the Supporting Document for the Network Code on Operational Security (NC OS) from ENTSO-E [3] as any measures applied by a TSO in order to fulfil the N-1 CRITERION and to maintain OPERATIONAL SECURITY LIMITS. They are categorized by preventive (i.e. pre-fault) or corrective (i.e. post-fault or curative) remedial actions within one TSO area or between interconnected TSOs. But based on this supporting document, the different types of remedial action are defined as:

- PREVENTIVE REMEDIAL ACTIONS are used normally in OPERATIONAL PLANNING or scheduling stage to maintain system in NORMAL STATE in the coming operational situation and to prevent propagation of DISTURBANCE outside the TSO's responsibility area.
- CORRECTIVE REMEDIAL ACTIONS are actions, which will be implemented immediately or relatively soon after an occurrence of a CONTINGENCY, which leads to a state differing from normal state. With the corrective remedial action the system will be returned back to normal state.

In order to be exhaustive, tools for assessing the security of power system situations should simulate not only the impact of the contingencies selected by the operator but also the efficiency of remedial actions adopted in case of VIOLATIONS caused by these contingencies. It is not necessary to warn the operator when corrective remedial actions (identified in advance by the operator and/or obtained from an optimization module) have been proven to be efficient to keep the system in a secure state. Nevertheless the operator has to be made aware of the situation and in case of an effect on a neighbouring TSO-grid these corrective remedial actions have to be agreed upon. When corrective remedial actions are not sufficient to alleviate all the constraints, the operator needs to know which preventive remedial actions must be put in place and at what time.

There is a large number of available preventive and corrective remedial actions and this number of possible measures is growing as the flexibility of the grid is increasing. Classical grid expansion and new controllable devices, e.g. PSTs and HVDC lines, offer new types of control actions on the power flows and an increased flexibility in the power system. Overall this leads to an amount of possible remedial actions beyond the point, where manual determination of remedial actions based on operational experience would be sufficient. The next generation of simulation tools under development by iTesla and UMBRELLA that will be available to operators in the coming years to assess the security of power system situations will take this into account.

Therefore exist a need to have a common understanding of modelling of contingencies and of preventive and corrective remedial actions among European TSOs and a common exchange format as already explained in Chapter 3.1. Especially with respect to an automatic security constrained optimization, a clear unambiguous modelling of the different kind of remedial actions is needed (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Different TSO strategies regarding current limits lead to different operation strategies. This has to be modelled adequately in order to achieve reasonable calculation results.

More precisely, the preventive and/or corrective remedial actions that should be taken into account can include several kinds of elementary actions. The most common ones are the following:

- Topology changes.
- Changes of set point values of PSTs.
- Changes in reactive power injections e.g. capacitors, coils, generator set points, static var compensators (SVCs).
- Changes in transformer tap positions.
- Transfer of loads from one substation to another one.
- Changes in maintenance scheduling (some maintenance can be delayed or cancelled).
- Generation redispatching and/or start of a generation unit.

Moreover the existing different frameworks for the TSOs lead to different merit orders of remedial actions. To achieve the optimal remedial action(s) with the developed tools, a common proposal of order of remedial actions is obligatory.

Contingencies must also be specified with a sufficient degree of accuracy. Especially regarding a common methodology to determine the relevant contingencies for N-1 calculations at European level, e.g. if a generator fails it has the same effect as the failure of the line connecting the generator to the grid.

For the moment, there is no standardized format in the ENTSO-E profile able to describe contingencies and remedial actions. This format has to be defined and has to be consistent with the description of the system provided by CGMES files. All contingencies and remedial actions must be described with links to the associated devices. For instance a remedial action that operates a breaker must contain a reference to the CIM ID⁹ of the associated CIM switch. It is very important to notice that the CIM IDs must remain consistent so that a remedial action can be applied on different time steps.

To ensure that the results of the innovative tools can be used most effectively, an open, transparent exchange of all needed data is necessary.

Recommendation 3

In addition to stationary data of their respective system, European TSOs should exchange a list of contingencies to be simulated or the methodology to determine the contingencies as well as a catalogue of relevant remedial actions. Moreover a harmonization of the merit order of remedial actions is needed to be able to get common proposals of remedial actions from the new tools developed by itesla and UMBRELLA. The exchange format needs to be consistent with the description of the system (use of CGMES with unique and persistent identifiers).

⁹ CIM ID: Common Information Model Identifier

3.4 Exchange of dynamic data in the future transmission system operation

There is a broad consensus among the European TSOs on the need to take into account the effect of dynamic phenomena on the power grid in the future transmission system operation. There are several reasons for this:

- The European grid is (and will be) operated closer to stability limits than in the past. This was underlined for instance by the detailed study of the situation of the European grid before the disturbance that occurred on November 4th, 2006 even if stability issues were not the root cause of this disturbance.
- TSOs are operating the power system as close as possible to the stationary limits (thermal current limits, always considering N-1 criterion) and they are also trying to increase these limits. The collateral result is that the system is getting closer to the stability limits.
- There are more and more power electronic devices on the grid with dynamic behaviours that must be considered (such as offshore wind parks, HVDC links and their converters, SVCs and other types of flexible AC transmission system (FACTS) with more or less fast dynamic behaviours).
- At the same time, a loss of “real inertia” takes place due to the shutdown of thermal units.
- Large cross-border power flows over long distance due to increasing market based power exchange are now more frequent.
- Wind generation, especially off-shore, can increase the risk of power oscillations as it increases the distance between the generation and the load centres.
- Enlargement of the European synchronous grid by connecting additional members, e.g. Turkey and probably other interconnectors in the future.
- Some particular events or configurations of the power system can lead to the occurrence of poorly-damped inter-area oscillations (e.g. frequency oscillations that happened between Italy and Denmark on February 19th and 24th, 2011).

Today most of the TSOs are already taking into account dynamic phenomena in their security assessment in one way or another, but very rarely in a systematic way, from two days ahead to real time using all available files (D2CF, DACF, IDCF and snapshot files¹⁰) updated regularly. The need to take into account dynamic phenomena in a more systematic way in operation was fully confirmed by a survey made among the iTesla TSOs at the beginning of the project (see public iTesla deliverable D1.1 “Formulation of the overall problem encountered by TSOs”).

Therefore the next generation of tools that will be made available to operators in the coming years to assess the security of power system situations over a time span from two days ahead to real time will include functionalities for accurate time domain simulations, potentially from a local geographical perimeter up to the pan-European one. These models will simulate the dynamic behaviour of generators, control systems, protections and all other components with fast dynamic behaviours. They will detect every possible dangerous dynamic phenomenon that could

¹⁰ A snapshot is a file which shows the state of the system at a particular point of time.

occur in case of contingency N-1/N-k or in case a remedial action is put in place by the operator to alleviate a constraint.

These dangerous phenomena could be:

- Exceeding of limit values (current and voltage) during the transient period before reaching a stable state.
- Loss of synchronism of one (or several) generator(s).
- Voltage collapse.
- Cascading outages.
- Low-frequency inter-area oscillations.

Thus our next recommendation is the following:

Recommendation 4

European TSOs should exchange dynamic data of their respective system to be able to run time domain simulations on all or parts of the European system in the framework of systematic security assessment of system situations from D-2 to close to real time.

More precisely, the dynamic data which are needed are the following:

- Generating units:
 - Detailed generator models (including wind turbines).
 - Speed and power regulator (turbine control).
 - Voltage regulator and excitation systems with their limitations.
 - Power system stabilizers (PSS).
- Loads and controllable devices:
 - Load models (including induction machines, highly non-linear loads as aluminium smelters, etc.).
 - Controllable devices (FACTS, HVDC, etc.) and any other power electronic-based controllable devices.
 - Regulation control systems used in any of the above.
- Protection devices (line protections, busbar protections, over-current protections, loss of synchronism protections, over- and under-frequency protections, over- and under-voltage protections).
- Centralized voltage control.
- Any other kinds of control system.

3.5 Recommendation regarding the format of exchange of dynamic data

3.5.1 Problem encountered when exchanging dynamic data

It has to be mentioned that stationary data is something well-known and a common understanding of the models of stationary devices (stationary generators, lines, transformers, stationary loads, etc.) has been easily reached by all TSOs even with use of different simulation tools. This has been verified through CIM interoperability tests conducted by ENTSO-E, checking the load flow results performed on those CIM files using different tools. However, this process regarding stationary data cannot be transposed to dynamic data for several reasons:

- *Common understanding of devices with complex dynamic behaviours is very difficult (even for standard dynamic models) and sometimes nearly impossible:* Up to now, model exchange was about exchanging parameters on commonly understood models, supposing the equations used along with those parameters were unambiguously the same for all. This is of course not the case, for example, for a rotating machine, the different characteristics of the windings can be exchanged, supposing that the Park's equations are commonly assumed but the number of windings, or the saturation modelling might differ. In this case, exchanging identical parameters (correctly interpreted from both sides) will not guarantee identical results, because the equations might differ.
- *Software limitations:* Some software is not able to simulate complex devices or only with simplifications, leading again to different simulation results when comparing the time series issued from two different simulators. This is expected, but significant amount of time is always spent to find the origin of the differences: Is it a misinterpretation of parameters coming from another software format or is it a limitation/simplification of one of the two solvers in its integration algorithm? This highlights a clear need to decouple the specification of the model from the simulation tool.
- *Loss of information from one format to another one:* Translation from one proprietary format to another one always brings loss of information even for standard models.
- *Use of "user defined" models:* Some software offer flexibility to describe non-standard controls using its own internal language, increasing the issues raised in the three previous bullets.

3.5.2 Short-term solution proposed for the exchange format of dynamic data among European TSOs

The short-term solution relies on the exchange of:

- Data in CGMES format as already explained in the Recommendation 1.
- Dynamic models in native formats, i.e. in the original dynamic formats used by TSOs for their own dynamic studies (for instance in PSS[®]E or EUROSTAG[®] format in the iTesla consortium).
- A table of association to map the CIM ID of any stationary component (for example the ID of a generator) with a dynamic model (for example the dynamic model of a

synchronous machine), either a standard model or a “user defined” model. This association should also include the values of associated parameters.

Note that standard dynamic models of some TSOs are also available in the actual format of the CIM for dynamics. However, several issues make this alternative for now less interesting than data from TSOs in their own native format: some TSOs have provided very basic info in CIM with default parameter values, compared to the data available in their own native format. Moreover, as an example, some regulators, widely used at RTE are not in the CIM for dynamic reference, leading to the impossibility to communicate those models to other TSOs without an evolution of the format, which could take a long time. It is unlikely that the version of the CIM for dynamic data, which is under preparation, will be ready soon. As a consequence, providing native format as a short term recommendation is the best option.

Recommendation 5

In the short term, European TSOs should exchange dynamic data using standard or “user defined” models in the format they use for their internal dynamic studies.

3.6 Long term solution proposed for the exchange format of dynamic data among European TSOs (iTesla)

3.6.1 Added value of the MODELICA[®] language

When choosing a way to exchange dynamic data, several constraints have to be addressed:

- Find a solution where the issue of ambiguity of dynamic modelling is addressed.
- Be vendor independent: it is not acceptable to have a limited solution based on a specific software data format (PSS[®]E, EUROSTAG[®], PowerFactory or any other commercial product).
- Competition between simulators should remain open so that the best solver could be used (performance, accuracy, tool adapted to the nature of the phenomena to be simulated: slow/fast transient or voltage stability).
- Keep the “user defined” flexibility because new complex devices need to be modelled and it is not acceptable to wait for a new version of a given simulator/format to take it into account.
- Minimize the work to be done by the data providers (i.e. TSOs).

As a consequence, the MODELICA language appears to be most promising alternative. The main advantages of using this approach are:

- MODELICA is a language, not a software,
- It is equation based, not only parameters but also equations are explicitly exchanged in order to address “ambiguity” issues and flexibility.

3.6.2 Open Source MODELICA[®] Library

In the framework of the iTesla project, a Power System MODELICA[®] Library has been built with several (or all in some cases) dynamic models used by iTesla TSOs, namely, Statnett, REN, IPTO, Elia, RTE, whose reference software implementation is either in PSS[®]E or EUROSTAG[®]. All those models have been translated into a MODELICA[®] equivalent, validated against their reference software and put in the library. For instance, reference [4] describes the software to software validation tests carried out to validate RTE’s models originally defined in EUROSTAG[®]. As RTE has access to all equations in EUROSTAG[®]’s source code, it was possible to transpose them exactly into MODELICA[®] equations. In addition, reference [5] presents the approach used to perform software-to-software validation for PSS[®]E models typically used by Statnett and REN. This Power System MODELICA[®] Library is about to be released as an open source library under a LGPL license so that this library is used and enriched by the TSO and the ‘power systems’ community.

Note that the translation from proprietary models to MODELICA[®] is possible with no loss of information even for user defined models, but the other direction is not possible since MODELICA[®] offers a more general way to define a system with differential-algebraic equations.

3.6.3 Long-term solution proposed by iTesla

The proposed long-term solution relies on the exchange of CGMES files (which include stationary and dynamic data) and on links between these files and the MODELICA® library described above.

Then it is possible to associate the CIM ID of any dynamic model to which it is referred in a CGMES file (standard model or “user defined” model) with one model of the MODELICA® library.

Figure 14: Long term solution proposed by iTesla.

After that, it is possible to build a full MODELICA® representation of the grid (stationary + dynamic data) for any CGMES file, ready to be used by a simulation engine compatible with the MODELICA® language (proprietary or open source software).

This solution will encourage vendors to develop tools compliant with the MODELICA® language. This would have the following main advantages:

- A common, standardized and open equation-based modelling language and parameter exchange data format with a common understanding of the models in it,
- The creation of a truly free market place for modelling and simulation tool vendors, which would encourage solutions that focus on accuracy and performance using the exact same data in input (thereby decoupling of modelling and solving),
- A compliance with what has already been done for stationary data exchange among European TSOs (CIM stationary),

- Flexibility to define new models without the need to update the version of the exchange format (new equations are put in the library, references are still stored in the CIM dynamic file).

Recommendation 6 (iTesla)

European TSOs should exchange CGMES files of their respective system and it is proposed to encourage the power system community to use the open source iTesla Power System MODELICA[®] library to be able to run time domain simulations on all or parts of the European system using MODELICA[®] language compliant simulation engine.

3.7 Risk management and reliability criteria

Risk-based security assessment accounts for both the probability that an event happens, and the severity of such an event (typically measured in terms of cost). Conceptually, the risk of a contingency can thus be evaluated as:

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Probability} \cdot \text{Severity}$$

Currently, there is no explicit calculation of risk in operational planning or real-time operation.

Since the N-1 criterion considers the risk of outages only implicitly (i.e., no differentiation between the probability of different outages or the severity of the resulting operating conditions), costly measures are implemented to resolve N-1 violations with low risk, e.g., where the amount of customers hit by a failure would be marginal, the probability of the initial failure is negligible or the N-1 violation would cause no further cascading.

On the other hand, which is the worst case from the perspective of a TSO, an N-1 secure state might not be sufficiently safe due to the possibility, that more than one single network element trips. Although this is a rare event with low probability, the severity of such an event might be high, leading to a significant risk. Furthermore, even though the forecasted system state was N-1 secure, uncertainty due to intra-day energy trades and forecast errors regarding power injections from RES power plants might lead to frequent violations of the N-1 criterion in real-time operation. To incorporate this risk in operational planning, the development of common probabilistic security criteria and methods to exchange more comprehensive forecasts for power injections (not only a point forecast, but several scenarios or probabilistic forecasts) are necessary.

Thus, relevant data concerning an adequate assessment of risk are mainly:

- Estimates of the (cost of) energy not served.
- Reliability data and/or failure probabilities of equipment.
- Failure probabilities of remedial actions.
- Probabilistic forecasts for RES and load.
- Scenarios for intra-day electricity trading.

Recommendation 7

European TSOs should be encouraged to develop and include common risk-based criteria for security assessment in their operational planning process and real-time operation. In particular, these criteria should include data related to reliability and/or failure rates of equipment, estimates of the (cost of) energy not served, as well as more comprehensive forecasts to describe uncertainties from RES, load and intra-day trading.

3.8 Defence and restoration plans

ENTSO-E is analysing power system security based on a conceptual classification of the system operating conditions into the system states Normal, Alert, Emergency, Blackout and Restoration, and the defence plan is composed of a Special Protection Scheme and a System Protection Scheme [6]. The system states and the function of each of the two defence plan components are illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 15: System states and defence plans.

Whether based on the N-1 criterion or on alternative probabilistic security criteria, there will inevitably be a risk of exceptional contingencies and related system responses, e.g. due to cascading events which are not considered by the online security assessment, and even though the probability of such occurrences is very low, the impact may be very severe deterioration of the system to a more critical state (emergency state or even a black-out).

The growing deployment of embedded HVDC connections offers new opportunities for power flow control, which can be utilized in defence plans. E.g. research in the iTesla project has shown how a tool to provide emergency control of embedded HVDC links can be applied to manage inter-area oscillations during emergencies using a modified Nordic 32-bus system as test case [1]. This is illustrated in Figure 16,

Figure 16: Managing inter area oscillations using emergency control of embedded HVDC links in a modified Nordic32 system as test case. The left graphs show the instable response without emergency control, and right shows the response with HVDC emergency control.

In the 4 November 2006 case, the European system was separated into 3 areas, of which the North East area was left with surplus generation causing critical over-frequencies. As stated in UCTE’s final report about the case, “the uncontrolled operation of dispersed generation (mainly wind and combined-heat-and-power) during the disturbance complicated the process of re-establishing normal system conditions” [7]. Modern wind power plants include frequency control, which can be applied to implement over-frequency emergency control. PV units could also contribute, but PV units are usually much smaller and therefore the implementation in a significant part of the PV plants will be more costly. A synthetic use case where Germany and Denmark West is separated with surplus generation is used below to illustrate the possible impact of wind power over-frequency control [1]. For under-frequency emergency control, demand side response could also be considered.

Figure 17: Managing over-frequency emergencies using wind power plant control in a synthetic case where Germany and Denmark West is separated with surplus generation.

The installation of PMUs in power systems is growing fast, but at the present stage, TSOs do not use the PMU information in defence plans or in restoration processes. In the iTesla project, a defence plan methodology against voltage instability has been developed and validated using a hardware-in-the-loop setup. In addition, a methodology for automatic tuning of out-of-step (OOS) relay tuning has been developed and verified [1].

Restoration plans aim to reduce the duration of power system interruptions. In the iTesla project, two solutions have been developed and verified with this purpose in mind. The first solution is to automatically compute coordinated restoration plans which take into account the dynamics of the system. This solution is verified using AGORA to compute restoration plan and FAST DTS to provide dynamic simulation of the plan actions as illustrated in Figure 17 [8]. The second solution is to use RES in the restoration process. Simulated study cases have been used to verify that the use of onshore and offshore wind power plants can reduce the restoration time.

Recommendation 8

European TSOs are encouraged to continue the ongoing work towards harmonization of defence plans and restoration procedures, and consider to integrate solutions for coordinated power flow control of embedded HVDCs to dampen inter-area oscillations, over-frequency control of RES generation and frequency control of consumption to defend the frequency stability, and use of PMU information for early detection of voltage instability and use tools for automatic tuning of out-of-step relays. There is also a need to consider the impact of the steadily increasing amount of distributed generation on the existing load shedding schemes. Finally, the TSOs should consider using automatically computed coordinated restoration plans taking into account dynamics and further investigate possibilities of using AC and DC connected controllable wind power plant to speed up restoration.

3.9 Amendment of operational security processes & tools

As stated in the previous chapters there is an increasing complexity in transmission system operation induced by the increasing amount of RES and cross-border trading. Therefore the future security assessment tools developed by iTesla and UMBRELLA will support operational planners in a coordinated way by finding a common optimal solution for different congestions and different combinations of uncertainties taking time dependent conditions into account. Practical tests in the toolbox prototypes and operational experience show, that it is essential to determine, evaluate and implement remedial actions in a (semi-automated) coordinated way. The iterations caused by shifting of congestions from one TSO to another TSO due to the implementation of remedial actions with different priorities need to be avoided.

Figure 18: Example of heterogeneous order of (remedial) measures by different TSOs' operating rules due to the non-harmonized legal/regulatory frameworks, with focus on the use of multilateral remedial actions (MRA) within the TSC-region¹¹.

The Network Codes, especially the NC OS, drafted by the ENTSO-E and enacted by the European Commission were an important step along the path of the harmonization of legal/regulatory frameworks within the European electricity system. But in order to achieve the best possible solutions in terms of a European optimum a further harmonization and clarification is needed, which is not addressed in this level of detail by the network codes. Since the non-harmonized legal/regulatory frameworks within the different European countries are basis of the local implementation of TSO operating rules, there is currently a wide variety of the order of the

¹¹ TSC: TSO Security Cooperation

different remedial actions (see Figure 18). This significantly complicates the operational planning/real-time operation, because a straightforward, security constrained optimization is impossible. Therefore the legal/regulatory frameworks within the European countries and neighbouring stakeholders have to be further harmonized in order to be able to actually achieve the best possible solutions in terms of a European optimum. Legal/regulatory framework is in this context also concerning the market mechanisms in the individual countries and the market coupling mechanisms between them (see the case study of UMBRELLA Deliverable 4.3 *'Methods for optimization of power transits'* [9]). The legal/regulatory framework has to be appropriate for each TSO in order to implement/activate the coordinated actions at the coordinated time in the aligned quality and quantity. Also appropriate cost sharing principals/procedures will help to support the readiness of the TSOs to implement the results of the innovative tools in their operational practice. An optimal solution in terms of a fundamental physical and economical consideration on a regional level, covering a significant part of Europe, should not be jeopardized by a "national optimization strategy". The most promising approach in order to achieve this is a strong cooperation among the national regulations authorities.

Recommendation 9

The experience of the TSOs shows that for the successful daily operation the European TSOs should further develop and harmonize their processes regarding operational planning and real-time operation, incorporating the preferable functionalities from the research projects.

Support from legal and regulatory side is needed in order to achieve the best possible solutions in terms of a European optimum. The most promising approach in order to achieve this is a strong cooperation among the national regulations authorities.

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5 Glossary

In order to identify common terms of this glossary when used in this deliverable, all terms listed in this glossary will be formatted in a “CAPITALISED” manner in the first reference to a term in the Chapter 3 *Recommendations to ENTSO-E*.

Contingency	<p>Contingency is the unexpected failure or outage of a system component, such as a generator, transmission line, circuit breaker, switch, or other electrical element. A contingency also may include multiple components, which are related by situations leading to simultaneous component outages. [10]</p> <p>Contingency means the identified and possible or already occurred fault of an element within or outside a TSO’s responsibility area, including not only the transmission system elements, but also significant grid users and distribution network elements if relevant for the transmission system operational security. Internal contingency is a contingency within the TSO’s responsibility area. External contingency is a contingency outside the TSO’s responsibility area, with an influence factor higher than the contingency influence threshold. [3]</p>
Corrective Remedial Action	<p>In real-time operation are the rendered necessary actions to restore the corrective (or curative) remedial actions are actions, which will be implemented immediately or relatively soon after an occurrence of a contingency, which leads to a state differing from normal state. With the corrective remedial action the system will be returned back to normal state. [3]</p>
Disturbance	<p>Disturbance means an unplanned event that may cause the transmission system to divert from normal state. [3]</p>
Fault	<p>All types of short-circuits: single-, double- and triple-phase, with and without earth contact. It means further a broken conductor, interrupted circuit, or an intermittent connection, resulting in a permanent non-availability of the affected transmission system element. [3]</p>
Generation	<p>Generation is the rate at which a generation set delivers electric power to a system or part of a system, generally expressed in kilowatts (kW) or megawatts (MW), at a given instant or averaged over any designated interval of time. [10]</p>
Generation Set	<p>A generation set is a set of machines consisting of a generator (and its driving apparatus) and a turbine of a generation unit. [10]</p>
Injection	<p>Action of feeding electricity into the system. [11]</p>

<i>N-1 Criterion</i>	The N-1 criterion is a rule according to which elements remaining in operation after failure of a single network element (such as transmission line / transformer or generation unit, or in certain instances a busbar) must be capable of accommodating the change of flows in the network caused by that single failure. [10]
<i>N-1 Situation</i>	The situation in the transmission system in which a contingency from the contingency list has happened. [11]
<i>Normal State</i>	The system state where the system is within operational security limits in the N-Situation and after the occurrence of any contingency from the contingency list, taking into account the effect of the available remedial actions. [11]
<i>Preventive Remedial Action</i>	Preventive remedial actions are used normally in operational planning or scheduling stage to maintain system in normal state in the coming operational situation and to prevent propagation of disturbance outside the TSO's responsibility area. [3]
<i>Operational Planning</i>	Operational planning is the system operators' planning of the operation of the power system. [11]
<i>Operational Security</i>	The transmission system capability to retain a normal state or to return to a normal state as soon and as close as possible, and is characterised by thermal limits, voltage constraints, short-circuit current, frequency limits and stability limits. [11]
<i>Operational Security Limits</i>	The acceptable operating boundaries: thermal limits, voltage limits, short-circuit current limits, frequency and dynamic stability limits. [3]
<i>Remedial Action (i.e. remedies or remedial measures)</i>	Any measure applied by a TSO or several TSOs, manually or automatically, in order to maintain operational security. In particular, remedial actions serve to fulfil the N-1 criterion and to maintain operational security limits. [3]
<i>Uncertainty(ies)</i>	Possible deviation between the deterministic forecast and the real-time measurement.
<i>Violation</i>	Infringement of operational security limits after a case of disturbance in system operation.